

NOTES

Mixed Thiocyanato Complexes of Chromium(III)

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Manuscript received 26 September 1989,
accepted 10 April 1990

WE report here the preparation and characterisation of some new thiocyanato complexes of chromium(III) with anthranilic acid (Hantr), salicylaldehyde (Hsal), *o*-hydroxyacetophenone (HOap) and 8-hydroxyquinoline (HOxin).

Experimental

Ligands used were extra pure reagent (BDH or E. Merck) and $K_3[Cr(NCS)_6] \cdot 4H_2O$ was prepared by reported method¹.

Preparation of complexes $[CrL_2(NCS)(H_2O)] \cdot 2H_2O$ (LH=HOxin or Hantr), $[Cr(HOap)(Oap)(NCS)_2]$ and $[CrL_2(NCS)]_2$ (LH=HOap or Hsal): Mixed ethanolic solutions of $K_3[Cr(NCS)_6] \cdot 4H_2O$ (0.005 mol) and ligand (0.01 mol, 30 ml) were refluxed for 1 h on a steam-bath and concentrated to 10–15 ml and diluted with cold water (40 ml). The resulting tarry mass was filtered and recrystallised with hot aqueous ethanol. In case of 8-hydroxyquinoline, a little less soluble trischelate $[Cr(Oxin)_3] \cdot 2H_2O$ was obtained which was removed by filtration. The complex $[Cr(Oap)_2(NCS)]_2$ was prepared by heating $[Cr(HOap)(Oap)(NCS)_2]$ in an air-oven at 100–110°.

The results of elemental and physical data of the complexes are given in Table 1. The magnetic moment, uv and ir spectra were recorded as reported earlier¹.

Results and Discussion

The complexes are stable but the hydrated complexes $[CrL_2(NCS)(H_2O)] \cdot 2H_2O$ (LH=HOxin or Hantr) gradually lose water molecules and are converted into $[CrL_2(NCS)(H_2O)]$ below 110°. The remaining water molecule of $[CrL_2(NCS)(H_2O)]$ is not lost before decomposition which indicates that one water molecule of hydrated complexes $[CrL_2(NCS)(H_2O)] \cdot 2H_2O$ is bonded to the metal atom. The complexes are soluble in DMF and hot ethanol.

The ethanol or DMF solution of the complexes are non-conducting indicating non-ionic character of the complexes. The complexes display normal magnetic moment value at room temperature (305 K) similar to octahedral chromium(III). The electronic reflectance spectra of complexes display ligand field transitions in the regions 22 700–24 400 and 17 240–18 690 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (F) and ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (F) transitions in octahedral field². The ligand field parameters Dq , B and β values have been found to be in the range 1 724–1 780, 542–605 and 0.59–0.66 cm^{-1} respectively. The energy of Dq for the complexes is in the range of that for hexaquo- and hexathiocyanatochromate(III).

The ir spectra of complexes display a broad and strong band at 2 060–2 080 cm^{-1} (C≡N) and a weak band at 780–810 cm^{-1} (C=S) similar to N-bonded thiocyanato complexes^{3,4}. An additional broad shoulder at 2 030–2 040 cm^{-1} observed in case of $[Cr(oap)_2(NCS)]_2$ and $[Cr(Sal)_2(NCS)]_2$ is attributed to splitting of $\nu_{C=N}$ vibration indicating bridging nature of the N-bonded thiocyanato molecule in these complexes³. The hydrated or aquo complexes display a broad band near 3 450 cm^{-1} attributable to ν_{OH} of water molecule. A medium broad band at 830 ± 10 cm^{-1} in complexes $[CrL_2(NCS)(H_2O)] \cdot 2H_2O$ (LH=HOxin or Hantr) suggests the coordinated nature of water molecule⁵.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd	Colour	Analysis % · Found/(Calcd)			μ_{eff} B M.
		M	N	NCS	
$[Cr(antr)_2(NCS)(H_2O)] \cdot 2H_2O$	Bluish green	11 71 (11 92)	9 54 (9 63)	13 51 (13 31)	3 96
$[Cr(Oxin)_2(NCS)(H_2O)] \cdot 2H_2O$	Reddish brown	11 58 (11 49)	9 00 (9 29)	13 01 (12 84)	3 73
$[Cr(HOap)(Oap)(NCS)]_2$	Greenish yellow	11 91 (11 83)	6 41 (6 38)	26 53 (26 43)	3 76
$[Cr(Oap)_2(NCS)]_2$	Brownish yellow	13 34 (13 67)	3 41 (3 68)	15 58 (15 27)	3 81
$[Cr(Sal)_2(NCS)]_2$	Greenish yellow	14 51 (14 76)	4 12 (3 98)	16 69 (16 49)	3 74

The complexes $[\text{CrL}_2(\text{NCS})_2]$ ($\text{LH}=\text{Hsal}$ or HOap) and $[\text{Cr}(\text{HOap})(\text{Oap})(\text{NCS})_2]$ display ν_{CO} band at $1640-1615\text{ cm}^{-1}$ whereas the free ligand displays this band in the region $1650-1680\text{ cm}^{-1}$. A marked shift in the ν_{CO} vibration suggests the bonding of ketonic oxygen to metal atom⁶. The $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ of phenolic group is shifted to higher wave number (1325 for Hsal and 1330 cm^{-1} for HOap complexes) from free ligand (1170 and 1190 cm^{-1}) which suggest the coordination of deprotonated phenolic oxygen to chromium(III)⁶. The NH stretch of anthranilate group in $[\text{Cr}(\text{antr})_2(\text{NCS})(\text{H}_2\text{O})].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is not resolved and is observed as a broad band at $3300-3450\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to water molecule. However, NH_2 bending band is located at 1612 cm^{-1} which is lower than bending band 1634 cm^{-1} of free ligand, indicating the coordination of amino group nitrogen to the metal atom. The carboxyl group $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO})$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO})$ of anthranilate group is observed at 1570 and 1345 cm^{-1} as a broad band. The $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO})$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO})$ of free anthranilic acid is observed at 1520 and 1410 cm^{-1} . The red-shift of ν_{as} and blue-shift in $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO})$ vibrations suggest the unidentate nature of carboxylate group to metal atom⁷. The absence of ν_{OH} band and red-shift of $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ vibration (1275 cm^{-1}) of HOxin in $[\text{Cr}(\text{Oxin})_2(\text{NCS})(\text{H}_2\text{O})].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (free ligand displays $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ and 1100 cm^{-1})^{6,7} suggest the deprotonation and bonding of phenolic oxygen to metal. The ν_{CN} band of HOxin (1575 cm^{-1}) also shifts to higher frequency (1600 cm^{-1}) indicating the coordination of pyridine nitrogen to metal atom⁶. The ir spectra of the complexes could not be recorded in far-infrared region therefore, nothing could be said about M-L vibration.

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Copper(II) Complexes of 2-Alkoxy-4-amino/imino-6,7-diphenyl-7-oxo-1,3,5-triaza-1,3,5-heptatriene and 2,11-Dialkoxy-4,9-diamino/imino-6,7-diphenyl-1,3,5,8,10,12-hexaza-1,3,5,7,9,11-dodecahexene

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Manuscript received 28 September 1989,
accepted 11 May 1990

BIGUANIDES and *O*-alkylamidinoisourea have almost similar characteristics¹. Both of them are strong field ligands and can form complexes with metal ions in higher oxidation states². Their metal complexes exhibit pseudo-aromatic character³. The formation of Schiff bases with these ligands are expected to influence the stability and bonding parameters. The cryomagnetic and spectral studies of one such series of Schiff bases derived from biguanide and salicylaldehyde have been reported⁴. We have also reported⁵ copper(II) complexes with Schiff bases derived from *O*-alkylamidinoisourea and salicylaldehyde. The results of such investigation in which bridging groups have been introduced connecting two *O*-alkylamidinoisourea pertain to the present study.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of B.D.H. or E. Merck grade. Solvents were used as such.

Our attempt to isolate the ligand from the starting materials was futile. Hence the complexes were prepared *in situ* by template method by the reaction of cyanoguanidine, benzoin/benzil in the presence of the copper(II) salts.

$[\text{Cu}(\text{ADTH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_2\text{Cl}_2$: A mixture of cyanoguanidine (2 mmol) and benzoin (2 mmol) dissolved in methanol, was refluxed till all cyanoguanidine went into solution. A methanolic solution of $\text{CuCl}_2.2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2 mmol) and sodium acetate was added to it and the solution was refluxed for 2 h and then allowed to cool to room temperature. The resulting solid was washed with methanol and dried under reduced pressure over fused CaCl_2 . Other complexes were prepared by using different copper(II) salts and appropriate alcohols.

$[\text{Cu}(\text{DDHD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2$: A mixture of cyanoguanidine (2 mmol) and benzil (1 mmol) dissolved in methanol, was refluxed till all cyanoguanidine